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A vida DIY: Design e Arte das décadas de 1950 e 1960

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RESUMO

Esta pesquisa documental tem como objetivo identificar, a partir de uma atitude transdisciplinar, o surgimento do DIY como noção que influenciou o cotidiano durante as décadas de 1950 e 1960. Para atingir esse objetivo, este texto foi estruturado em duas seções dedicadas ao design e à arte, respectivamente. A primeira parte traça os primórdios das práticas DIY a partir de uma perspectiva de design, revisando os textos de Lichtman (2006) e Jackson (2006). A segunda parte aborda as origens das práticas DIY do ponto de vista da arte considerando a posição de Dezeuze (2012) e Calirman (2008) em que se destacam as contribuições de artistas vinculados ao fluxus e ao neoconcretismo brasileiro. Por fim, ambas as seções estão relacionadas a um conjunto de coincidências ideológicas que nos permitem redescobrir o “faça você mesmo” como um modo de vida que buscou a liberdade durante o período declarado.

Palavras-chave: Faça Você Mesmo; abrigo; barco; *fluxus*; neoconcretismo

ABSTRACT

This documentary research aims to identify, from a transdisciplinary attitude, the emergence of DIY as a notion that influenced everyday life during the 1950s and 1960s. To achieve such goal, this text has been structured in two sections dedicated to design and art respectively. The first part traces the beginnings of the DIY practices from a design perspective by reviewing the texts of Lichtman (2006) and Jackson (2006). The second part addresses the origins of DIY practices from an art viewpoint considering the position of Dezeuze (2012) and Calirman (2008) in which the contributions of artists assigned to fluxus and Brazilian neoconcretism stand out. Finally, both sections are related to set ideological coincidences that allow us to rediscover “do it yourself” as a way of life that pursued freedom during the stated period. Keywords: do-it-yourself; shelter; boat; fluxus; neoconcretism

INTRODUCTION

Research about Do-it-yourself (DIY) practices has barely been made from independent disciplines, such as design and art. On one hand, from the design field, Jackson (2006) has admitted that “academic investigations of do-it-yourself activity are notable for their scarcity”¹. On the other hand, from the art field, Dezeuze (2012) has declared that “while many recent texts and exhibitions acknowledge the importance of 1960s do-it-yourself artworks, the

¹ JACKSON, Andrew. Labour as Leisure: The Mirror Dinghy and DIY Sailors. *Journal of Design History*, Oxford, Number 1, Volume 19, 57-67, 2006. p. 58

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relations between contemporary practices and their precedents remain largely unmapped”². Even so, the fact that she coined the term *DIY artworks* only twelve years ago proves that DIY art still needs to be theorized to understand better the practices made back then and now.

Even less studies have been produced from an approach that allows the examination of DIY beyond fields, which has encouraged us to write this paper. Our purpose is to point at DIY as a concept that was significant for both art and design during the 1950s and 1960s, a period in which the user/spectator’s involvement gained relevance. To achieve this goal, a transdisciplinary approach was used. Trans disciplinarity, explains Nicolescu (1996) “...encompasses...what is...between disciplines, through the different disciplines and beyond all discipline. Its purpose is to understand the present world, and one of its imperatives is the unity of knowledge.”³

This work has been structured in two sections. The first one reviews two articles that were written from the design field: Lichtman (2006), who focuses in security as a feature of DIY practices in the United States during the 1950s and 1960s; and Jackson (2006), who directs leisure as another characteristic of DIY practices in the United Kingdom during the same period. The second section examines two texts from the art domain. Dezeuze (2012), who traces the origins of DIY artworks in Europe, the United States and Brazil during the 1950s and 1960s; and Calirman (2008), who addresses the history of Brazilian performance, including artworks made after Neoconcretism that could relate to DIY practices as well. To conclude, both sections are linked to find correspondences in thought and to show that the transdisciplinary study of DIY practices can provide a wider way to understand them.

LICHTMAN (2006) AND JACKSON (2006): THE BEGINNINGS OF DIY DESIGN IN THE 1950S AND 1960S

This section aims to review two articles written from a design perspective to identify the

² DEZEUZE, Anna. An introduction to the 'do-it-yourself' artwork. In: DEZEUZE, Anna. *The 'do-it-yourself' artwork Participation from Fluxus to new media*. Manchester: Manchester University Press, 2012.1-21. p.5

³ NICOLESCU, Basarab. *La transdisciplinarietà. Manifiesto*. Hermosillo:7 Saberes, 2009. p.37

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origins of two prominent DIY endeavors in the 1950s and 1960s set in the United States and the United Kingdom respectively. The first article, written by Sarah A. Lichtman, is called *Do-It-Yourself Security: Safety, Gender, and the Home Fallout Shelter in Cold War America* and was published in the *Journal of Design History* in 2006. In it, the author explains that in the context of the Cold War, the government of the United States undertook several actions to promote the civil defense against a possible nuclear attack from Russia. One of the most important was a do-it-yourself home shelter.

According to Lichtman, three presidents contributed to foster the DIY home shelters. First, President Harry S. Truman founded the *Federal Civil Defense Administration* in 1951 and the idea of the shelter was considered following the idea of bomb shelters built in England during WWII. However, there was not enough money to continue with the shelter project, so cheaper ideas were preferred. The constant nuclear threat and the lack of funding took President Dwight D. Eisenhower in 1958 to create an initiative to encourage DIY shelters. A wide campaign in popular magazines, films and exhibitions was made and shelter plans were provided by the government upon request. President Kennedy defended the construction of shelters like any other president, and he even created a shelter program, but its price forced him to support DIY shelters.

Lichtman asserts that DIY practices as leisure were more popular than ever in the 1950s in the US; during the post-war new tools and materials appeared and contributed to the growth of home improvement DIY activities, while books and demonstrations made in stores taught people how to do reparations at home. However, she says, the productive and enjoyable leisure was reduced by the fear of a nuclear attack. The government combined DIY home improvement with security to convince Americans to get ready for war while doing a fun and satisfying activity. DIY shelters were shown as one of the projects that could be found in the 1950s in lifestyle magazines and that didn't need special skills, such as *Time* or *Popular mechanics*.

There were many kinds of shelters, explains Lichtman. "They ranged from lean-tos, basic basement concrete boxes, and metal pipes lowered into garden holes, to much more elaborate

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shelters such as those belonging to the wealthy and to celebrities...⁴. Most of them were very uncomfortable. In the end, claims Lichtman, DIY shelters were unsuccessful despite the government effort and the convenience of plans. Only 3% of Americans built a shelter. The reasons for this result were variable. For some people self-building was difficult or expensive, and for some more the shelters were not effective as a shield against radiation. These last were right, says Lichtman, considering that a study made by a civil defense officer found out that barely 1% of the examined DIY shelters fulfilled the requirements to protect against radiation.

The second article, written by Andrew Jackson, is called *Labour as Leisure: The Mirror Dingy and DIY Sailors* and was also published in the *Journal of Design History* in 2006. In it, the author shows an outstanding DIY project that was born in the United Kingdom as an effort to make a leisure activity, sailing, available for everyone. According to Jackson, important transformations occurred in Britain between 1950 and 1980. The working week was reduced to 40 hours and workers had the right to have at least three holiday weeks a year, which would translate into more free time and money. In the later 1960s, says the author, many people had the chance to stop renting a dwelling and became owners, so home improvement wasn't only a need anymore, it was also seen to gain status.

In Britain, asserts Jackson, during the post-war period, the new mass media like magazines and television helped promoting DIY home improvement activities. As an example, the author presents *Practical Householder*, a magazine that was launched in 1955. Its editor F.J. Camm, says Jackson, opened the first number mentioning that the lack of skilled manpower and the rise of costs motivated DIY home improvement activities. Also, in the late 1950s 60% of its pages were dedicated to advertisements of DIY manufacturers, who in response to the growing interest in DIY activities were creating and selling new products and tools.

Over time, states Jackson, the DIY market evolved and so did the specialist magazines. For instance, explains the author, in the early 1960s the magazine *Practical Householder* wasn't focused on home maintenance anymore, but in design. It included plans to make furniture at

⁴ LICHTMAN, Sarah A. Do-It-Yourself Security: Safety, Gender, and the Home Fallout Shelter in Cold War America. *Journal of Design History*, Oxford, Number 1, Volume 19, 39-55, 2006. p.45

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home and around 1965 this kind of home built projects had replaced almost all the maintenance chores.

A key figure highlighted by Jackson was the DIY expert Barry Bucknell, who became the presenter of the *Do-it-yourself* show in 1955, and then hosted the *Bucknell's House* show that reached 5.5 million viewers in 1962, the same year in which he created the dinghy. These boats used to be expensive because they were hand made from solid wood on demand from a wealthy person. Bucknell, explains Jackson, found a way to build dinghies quickly and with a low budget. He took the technique from a canoe maker and used new materials like waterproof plywood (that was created during the war), glass fiber tape and polyester resin. The first prototype was seen by the journalist Paul Boyle who worked for the *Daily Mirror*, a newspaper that was looking for fresh ideas to promote itself. The boat got its name from it, the *Mirror dinghy*, and was launched in the London Boat show in 1963. It appeared for the first time in the newspaper in 1964.

The dinghy, describes Jackson, was 3.3 meters long and two adults could travel in it. It could be sailed, rowed, or motorized and it was so light that it could be moved on the car roof. It had a mast that was formed by two pieces to allow it to be stored inside of the ship and two people could build it without considering the finishes in around 50 hours. In 1963, the dinghy could be bought in three different versions, as a kit, as an unfinished version, and as a ready to sail version. Also, the buyers were offered credit.

Both, the newspaper and the boat, declares Jackson, were very successful. In 1964 *The Daily Mirror* reached 5 million readers, the highest number of readers in Europe. Even in our century, more than 70 thousand dinghies had been built in 2004 around the world. *The Daily Mirror*, claims the author, kept on advertising the dinghies during the 1960s until 1969, when a magazine that complemented the newspaper, the *Mirror Magazine*, was created for luxury market. The boat was marketed there in smaller ads. One year later, the magazine disappeared. In 1968 the boat brand included other kind of ships, but anyone was as popular as the *Mirror dinghy*.

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DEZEUZE (2012) AND CALIRMAN (2008): THE ORIGIN OF DIY ART IN THE 1950S AND 1960S

This section intends to explore two texts written from an art viewpoint to observe the beginning of DIY art in the 1950s and 1960s in Europe, the United States and Brazil independently. The first text, written by Anna Dezeuze, is named '*Open work*', '*do-it-yourself artwork and bricolage*' and is one of the fourteen essays that integrate *The 'do-it-yourself' artwork Participation from Fluxus to new media*, published in 2012. To explain the origins of DIY artworks, Dezeuze departs from the relationship between the term DIY and the French word *bricolage*, which according to the translator of the 1966 edition of *The Savage Mind* (Lévi-Strauss, 1961) "...can be associated with a variety of do-it yourself activities ranging from functional odd jobs to arts and craft hobbies"⁵.

According to Dezeuze (2012), the participation of spectators in art began separately in Europe and the Americas in the late 1950s and 1960s because of a general interest for artists in creating *open works* defined by Campos as "short organisations embodying a realm of possibilities (*um possível*) opposed to the fixity of conventional solutions of the perfect, classical artwork"⁶. Dezeuze compares the bricoleur's work (based on Lévi-Strauss) with the open works (based on Eco) considering that both processes are similar. The first one chooses means from leftover material, while the second one explores possibilities by arranging different elements. The leftover material used to produce open works, says Dezeuze, are the methods left in experimental poetry, geometric abstraction, and music during the post-war period. This could be seen, says the author, in the de Campos' concrete poetry that uses the word as a form, a sound or a meaning; in *The First National Exhibition of Concrete Art* (Sao Paulo, 1952), an abstract trend that was influenced by Max Bill and the idea that a line, a color, or a surface is more real than anything; and also in the Experimental Composition course that Cage started teaching in 1958, where some of his students who would become members of *Fluxus* like Brecht learned that since

⁵ DEZEUZE, Anna. 'Open work', 'do-it-yourself' artwork and bricolage. In: DEZEUZE, Anna. *The 'do-it-yourself' artwork Participation from Fluxus to new media*. Manchester: Manchester University Press, 2012.47-68. p.49

⁶ *Idem*

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duration is one of the elements of sound, any event that happened in time could be understood as sound too.

Fluxus and Concretism had a connection. Dezeuze says that some anthologies of concrete poetry included *Fluxus* poets and Maciunas used the word *concretism* in his manifesto of 1962. This happened, points the author, because these two groups shared mainly two desires: universality, which they searched by letting the visual, verbal or musical elements mean nothing but themselves; and objective reality, that they pursued by avoiding personal expression.

Participatory works, claims Dezeuze based on Maciunas, were born in the difference between the systematic composition methods (as those used by concrete painters, who chose colors based on math) or chance methods (first introduced by Cage) and the independent performer: An interesting parallelism can be noticed, says Dezeuze, when Fluxus musician Earle Brown changed the method that he used in his scores from mechanistic to intuitive, while the two concrete artists groups called *Ruptura* and *Frente* became opponents when some members of *Frente*, followed Ferreira Gullar, who founded the Neoconcrete group in Rio de Janeiro in 1959. Neoconcrete artists thought that concretism was too rational and preferred intuition that was related to real life. Two examples of neocroncrete artworks are *Lembra* (1959) by Gullar, a poem-object that consisted of a cube that could be removed by the spectators to discover a hidden word; and *Bichos*.

Do-it-yourself artworks are “a range of artistic practices that require an active physical and/or conceptual participation on the part of the spectator.”⁷ Dezeuze resumes the word *bricolage* and based on Lévi-Strauss, states that it was born in three fields (hunting, racing and games), which relate respectively with three of its features (contingency, movement and play). These three characteristics can be found, explains Dezeuze, in several Fluxus and Neoconcrete works, which relate them and distinguish them as DIY practices different from other participatory works of art that were produced in the late 1950s and 1960s.⁸

⁷ DEZEUZE, Anna. An introduction to the 'do-it-yourself' artwork. In: DEZEUZE, Anna. *The 'do-it-yourself' artwork Participation from Fluxus to new media*. Manchester: Manchester University Press, 2012.1-21. p.1

⁸ According to Dezeuze, DIY artworks developed in two waves during the 20th century. The first wave corresponds to the participation practices located in the 1960s and early 1970s, which were acknowledged in a little section of *Environments and Happenings* by Adrian Henri (1974); and which were traced in Europe and the Americas in *Art*,

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About contingency, Dezeuze explains that open works uncovered the emergency of themselves by showing how to disrupt close structures through particular events, as happened in assemblages made by bricoleurs. On movement, she mentions as examples Clark's *Bichos* and Brecht's exhibition *Toward Events*. *Bichos* (1960-1965) were a series of metal sculptures that could be arranged as the spectators decided, while Brecht's exhibition included a piece called *The Case* (1959) that invited the audience to handle or exchange the objects shown in a container. About games, she stresses economy as a characteristic that can be found in *DIY* artworks. As examples she includes the Brecht's and Higgins' scores that can be found in Young's *An Anthology* (1963). In *Motor vehicle sundown* (1960), for instance, Brecht asks performers to take a deck of 22 cards and to carry out what is written in them while sitting in a vehicle located in an exterior area. Instructions are as short as a single word, like "pause". Meanwhile, in *Constellation No. 1* (1959), Higgins explains the way a performance should be made using only three mandatory elements: 5 performers, 3 radios and 2 pianos. Lygia Pape's *Livro da criação* (1959) is also mentioned by Dezeuze as an example of economy because the creativity of the spectator is stimulated through simplicity, "each page is conceived as a set of components in a construction kit allowing participants to construct their own personal narratives of genesis"⁹

Over time some Fluxus artists, claims Dezeuze, changed the way they understood their previous works and the nature of their work from descriptive to instructive. As examples, the author presents Brecht who in 1961 noticed that his score *Drip music* (1959) could be performed in an everyday environment and that nothing was needed but being aware of that action. Another example is *Proposition* (1961) by Allison Knowles, in which the artist asks the spectators to prepare a salad. The critic Federico Morais (1970), explains Dezeuze, declared that after the end of Neoconcretism in 1962, Clark and Oiticica had overcome geometric abstraction and had moved forward to create tactile objects using everyday materials. This can be seen, says

Action and Participation by Frank Popper (1975). The second wave includes practices that were made in the 1990s and that became known thanks to *Relational Aesthetics* by Nicolas Bourriaud (1998) that centered in human relations; and *the Do it* project (that began in 1994) by Hans-Ulrich Obrist which focused on repetition.

⁹ DEZEUZE, Anna. 'Open work', 'do-it-yourself' artwork and bricolage. In: DEZEUZE, Anna. *The 'do-it-yourself' artwork Participation from Fluxus to new media*. Manchester: Manchester University Press, 2012.47-68. p. 59

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Dezeuze, in Clark's *Air and Stone* (1966), where the artist asks to hold a plastic bag filled with air and to balance a stone put on it; and in Oiticica's *Parangolés*.

The second text that was examined in this section, written by Claudia Calirman, is called *Naked Man, Flaming Chickens: A Brief History of Brazilian Performance Art* and was one of the twelve essays that integrate the book *Arte ≠ Vida Actions by artists of the Americas 1960-2000* which was published in 2008. Although Calirman doesn't mention the term do-it-yourself, she points at some of Oiticica, Clark and Pape's works, among others, that could be admitted as DIY artworks because of their central interest in the spectator's intervention and other features like contingency proposed by Dezeuze.

Calirman (2008) explains that Oiticica's *Parangolés* were colorful and layered capes that were first worn on August 12, 1965, by five members of the Mangueira samba school. Their intention was to enter the *Museu de Arte Moderna* of Rio de Janeiro for the opening of the *Opinion 65* exhibition, the first artists' response to the dictatorship that began in 1964 and continued up to 1985. Also, it transformed the status of the museum that had been exclusive for the elite until then.

Another another work that could be described as a DIY artwork is Pape's *Divisor* (1968) where the audience was asked to "stick their heads through holes cut out of a long cotton sheet, bringing them together as a unitary body in the crowd"¹⁰. In it the artist addresses the emergency of bringing together the Brazilian society of that time.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The *Do-it-yourself fallout shelter* promoted in the United States and the *Mirror dinghy* sold in the United Kingdom, were two DIY design cases located in the 1950s and 1960s that should be considered as outstanding (even if the shelter was unpopular) because they were promoted/traded for a long time, during the government of three American presidents and for

¹⁰ CALIRMAN, Claudia. *Naked Man, Flaming Chickens: A Brief History of Brazilian Performance Art*. In: *Arte≠Vida. Actions by artists of the Americas 1960-2000*. New York: El Museo del Barrio, 2008. 102-113. P. 107.

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over forty years respectively. They should also be considered as relevant because both allow us to notice that the global context of the Cold War and the circumstances of each country, featuring the lack of money and manpower as well as the need for protection and for leisure activities, were some of the reasons why DIY design practices originated during the stated period.

In the art field, during the same period, there was a general interest in creating open works, characterized by the existence of possibilities. Dezeuze identifies such openness in some of the Fluxus and Concrete works, linking both groups. The change to a more intuitive methodology, related to everyday life and centered in the involvement of the spectator took some Fluxus artists to transform the way they created art and to que birth of Neoconcretism separately. The DIY artworks made by some artists of both groups, states Dezeuze, share as features contingency, movement and play, which also separate them from other participatory practices. After the end of Neoconcretism (1962) some of the artists that were attached to it like Oiticica and Pape produced artworks that shared similar concerns and that were committed with social causes, as Calirman suggests.

Some works of design and art that were produced in the 1950s and 1960s approached DIY practices in their search for the user freedom, the spectator freedom, and ultimately the citizen freedom. The DIY fallout shelter was a government strategy that aimed to allow American inhabitants to live free of threatens; the *Mirror dinghy* was a product that intended to allow everybody to have free access to a leisure activity that used to be a privilege of a few; Clark's Bichos expected spectators to be free to move the sculptures as they wished; Brecht's *The Case* sought the public to freely exchange the objects. Even after the end of Neoconcretism, some works that could be considered as DIY (in the first wave) continued to be produced, such as Pape's *Divisor*, that made a call to become an only body or Oiticica's *Parangolés* that addressed the democratization of exhibition spaces and the liberation from the government oppression. Finally, although the cases presented in this work from the field of design and art are only a sample of the whole universe of DIY practices that were carried out in the 1950s and 1960s, it is possible to glimpse that the DIY spirit flooded the everyday life at that time, and also that it was deeply related with the struggle for freedom in both the social and the creation

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domains. The way other fields approached DIY during this period is yet to be explored.

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